

UTILIZATION OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION: ADVANTAGES, CHALLENGES AND PROSPECTS

^aMAIIA MOROZ, ^bYURII OREL, ^cVALENTYNA BOKLAG,
^dKATERYNA NABOKA, ^eNATALIIA PRYPUTA

^a*Municipal Institution of Higher Education "Bar Humanitarian Pedagogical College named after Mykhailo Hrushevsky", Bar, Ukraine.*

^b*Education and Research Institute "Institute of Public Administration", V.N. Karazin Kharkiv National University, Kharkiv, Ukraine.*

^{c,d}*Classic Private University, Zaporizhzhia, Ukraine.*

^e*Shupyk National Healthcare University of Ukraine, Kyiv, Ukraine.*

email: ^a*morozmaja@i.ua*, ^b*orel@karazin.ua*,
^c*boklag_val@ukr.net*, ^d*omka2387@gmail.com*,
^e*pryputa@ukr.net*

Abstract: Globalized trends regarding the transformation of the paradigm of social and socio-economic processes administration are leading to a reformatting towards intensifying the role of publicity and information accessibility. The study aims to provide a comprehensive analysis of the potential of innovative technologies in public administration. The research involved general scientific knowledge methods, including analysis, deduction and induction, comparison, and abstraction. The study considers various aspects of public administration based on the principles of sustainable development as an essential basis for the implementation of internal policy. The authors analyzed the main issues of applying innovative technologies in management processes and various ways to solve them. The article explored the potential optimization opportunities of the public management transformation process using innovative tools. The authors have studied the experience of developed countries in the public administration of society's life processes, public administration, and legal and organizational aspects. The research outcomes have a practical value for improving the modern management system by means of innovative technologies based on the principles of publicity and balanced development.

Keywords: globalization, digitalization, balance, efficiency, optimization, public administration, electronic governance, innovative technologies.

1 Introduction

The intensification of integration processes in the administrative activity system causes the formation of new challenges that require appropriate dynamic adaptive changes in the publicity vector. The concept of sustainable development, implemented to the maximum extent possible in the modern management paradigm, is seen as an optimal, socially effective, and socially oriented trend. The outlined approach seeks to realize the balanced development of society through the development and implementation of a set of organizational foundations, as well as effective means of their implementation and monitoring of efficiency. The potential of modern innovative technologies and digitalization plays a significant role in this process.

Ukrainian and foreign scholars consider the issue of public administration in the context of the intensification of digitalization and technological development in an interdisciplinary context. Some studies of contemporary scholars are devoted to the analysis of the functioning of public administration mechanisms in the context of globalization and the study of practical projects for their implementation. Thus, modern Ukrainian scholars (Volska, 2020; Masyk, 2023) explore the concept of public administration from the standpoint of the complexity and difficulty of the issue, taking into account the global digitalization of social and socio-economic processes.

When considering the essence of public administration in terms of innovative opportunities, some researchers (Pastuch, 2022; Vasylieva et al., 2020) emphasize that the potential and capabilities of public administration are fully revealed only through the harmonization of the main factors of the sustainable development concept, and based on the updated functionality in the public communications system. General public administration issues amidst the rapid development of innovative technologies are thoroughly investigated in the research of modern scientists (Prylypko, 2023). They analyze the risks and challenges related to the outlined process.

Certain conceptual issues are reflected in the studies by Vinuesa et al. (2020). Their results confirm the high priority of digitalization and the introduction of artificial intelligence tools into the public administration system. Despite the significant scientific contribution of modern scholars, some aspects of this issue still need to be studied.

The issues related to the development of an algorithm for the successful practical implementation of modern innovative capabilities in the public administration system in the context of global challenges and crisis phenomena of our time are still poorly studied. They require further scientific analysis. This study aims to analyze the potential of innovative technological tools for optimizing the public administration system for sustainable development and the dynamics of conceptual priorities in today's crisis conditions.

2 Literature review

The scientific and methodological framework of the studied issues is based on the research findings of scholars who focus on the aspects of implementing the principles of public administration in the context of sustainable development, the problems of transforming social processes towards digitalization, and the active involvement of innovative technologies, as well as finding ways to mitigate related risks. There are numerous publications on this topic in scientific professional journals. Some elements of innovative mechanisms of public administration in the context of sustainable development are discussed in the studies of many modern scientists (Roieva et al., 2023). The results of scientific research include studies (Noja, 2019; Esposito & Dicorato, 2020) that fundamentally substantiate the principles of effective implementation of public administration in the context of modern global challenges of a sustainable economy.

At the same time, some scholars (Bisongo, 2023; Massey, 2022) emphasize the complexity of introducing some aspects of innovative technologies into the public administration system due to the specifics of contemporary social processes. Many scientists (Meuleman, 2021; Deslatte & Stokan., 2020; Guarini et al., 2021) have formed the basic conceptual framework for an effective public administration system. They have actualized the need to introduce digitalization and electronic document management tools into public administration processes.

Therefore, despite the importance of the scientific and practical achievements of scholars on the studied issues, there is a need to continue research on aspects related to the outlined issues to ensure the sustainability of positive dynamics and preventive response to new challenges in public administration in the context of intensive development of innovative technologies.

3 Methods

A set of general methods of scientific cognition was applied during the research. These methods include abstract, logical, comparative analysis, induction, and deduction, methods of specification, abstraction, and formalization, as well as a tabular and graphical interpretation of theoretical information. The theoretical and methodological background of the study was formed by taking into account the key principles of comprehensive research based on a systematic approach. The complexity principle made it possible to analyze the object and subject of principle as a system with a corresponding set of interrelations.

The methods of analysis and synthesis were employed to identify the factors and stages of development of the studied object, as well as its defining elements. The comparison method was used to determine the specifics of development and features of innovative optimization of public administration in the

context of sustainable development. The deduction method was used to develop proposals for the vector of improvement of management processes based on the capabilities of digitalization processes. The inductive method was used to forecast indicators of future development.

The abstract-logical and dialectical methods of scientific cognition, as well as the method of scientific abstraction, were used to formulate theoretical generalizations, clarify the conceptual apparatus, identify basic concepts and categories, and formulate research conclusions. In addition, these methods were used to develop the concept of a holistic process of digital optimization of the management system in the context of sustainable development. The general scientific method of concretization was used to position the effectiveness and feasibility of increasing the role of innovative technologies in public administration during the implementation of socio-economic reforms.

4 Results

The modern concept of public administration sets the compliance with the current requirements of innovative technological solutions as the main prerequisite for its own implementation efficiency. The search for consensus between public administration actors in this area is determined by the priority vector of developing the public administration paradigm. Nowadays, a systemic approach to sustainable development is generally accepted in the main areas of public administration. They include financial and economic development, social transformation, and environmental safety guarantees.

The formation of a management system based on innovation potential involves consideration of available resource capacities, the priority of adaptability and prospective growth, as well as the synergy of national priorities and interests of local communities regarding the goals and means of development. The definition of public administration refers to the synergy of activities of state and local authorities, the private sector, and society in identifying and implementing management decisions of public importance within the limits of the powers and functionality defined by the legislation (Pastuch, 2022; Vasylyeva et al., 2020). Overall, public management covers the stages of planning, organizing, and controlling the implementation of management decisions. It involves the capabilities of modern information systems, digitalization tools, and regular performance monitoring.

The basic opportunities offered by an effective public administration system for modern society are depoliticization, prioritization of service users' interests, systematic quality monitoring, and continuous improvement. It is necessary to emphasize the partnership approach, which is positioned by the public administration system, where the state and citizens are equal participants in the relationship. Effective publicity is achieved with the help of modern technological capabilities. This includes electronic document management, digitalization of management processes, and the use of artificial intelligence tools.

By analyzing international experience in this area, it is possible to form certain conclusions about the benefits, risks, and challenges for each of them. In general, it can be argued that public administration systems in the context of the priority of sustainable development principles in developed countries are characterized by a focus on the active participation of society in management processes in various socio-economic spheres (Roieva et al., 2023).

The practical experience of developed countries can be used to formulate a strategy for the development of public administration in the context of sustainable development of Ukraine from the perspective of maximizing the use of innovative opportunities and digitalization tools. Globalization processes, which are typical nowadays, involve global economic, cultural, and political integration, which covers all spheres of public life and creates a system of interconnections and

interdependencies (Vinuesa et al., 2020). At the same time, changes in the governance system, decentralization of management processes, and the growing role of science, technology, and intelligence are inevitable. First and foremost, the principles of implementing modern innovative capabilities in the public administration paradigm focus on achieving decentralization, democracy, and adaptability to the needs of society (Table 1).

Table 1. Principles of public administration involving innovative technologies

Principle	Essence
Decentralization	Delegation (sectoral, regional, etc.) of management systems, financial autonomy of economic and investment processes
Prospects	The preference is given to technologies that have the potential for prolonged development in the future
Consistency	Selection of innovative tools based on the principle of complex multifactorial impact on administrative processes
Democratic nature	Intensification in the role of the public component within the public administration process
Adaptability	Possibility of dynamic changes while implementing strategic management under the influence of external and internal factors, following the principles of sustainable development
Monitoring	Regular analysis of the effectiveness and the need to update the tools of innovative public administration technologies based on performance evaluation

Source: authors observations

The need to transform the paradigm of public administration towards the use of digital technologies and innovative capabilities is driven by modern challenges in terms of data openness, access to decision-making procedures and control over their implementation, variability of corrective action, and effective performance analytics. Altogether, these dynamics will make it possible to ensure high quality of life indicators, as well as to significantly optimize and develop the public administration system (Figure 1).

An important issue for the establishment of public administration is to guarantee transparency, reliability, and relevance of informative data (Prylypko, 2023). Digitalization capabilities are the best option for communication in the system of modern public administration as a key factor in optimizing management mechanisms in order to simplify and autonomize processes. Electronic information systems allow for quick access to reference and statistical information and the collection and consolidation of necessary data. It should be noted that the active implementation of such systems in different countries as a central component of the transformation of public administration of socio-economic processes has highlighted several risks:

- The complexity of standardization and unification of documentation in different areas and organizations.
- Staff resistance to innovation.
- Passive participation of the population in the process.
- The lack of adequate quality software.
- Security of personalization and data transfer (Bisongo, 2023; Massey, 2022).

Today, the integration of artificial intelligence-based tools and methods into the public administration system is seen not only as a relevant strategy but also as a compelling necessity (Prylypko, 2023). This trend is confirmed by statistics showing that by 2025, 63% of management organizations in Europe plan to integrate artificial intelligence (Meuleman, 2021; Deslatte & Stokan, 2020; Guarini et al., 2021). The growing importance of artificial intelligence in management strategy indicates its significant potential in optimizing the threat detection process in the digitalized document environment. Nowadays, AI-powered tools are widely used to identify, monitor, and effectively

respond to cyberattacks. At the same time, they are marked by high levels of speed and accuracy.

Figure 1. Optimization of the public administration process based on innovative technologies
Source: compiled by the authors

Cybersecurity solutions based on artificial intelligence capabilities make it possible to identify suspicious activity and other abnormal actions with appropriate notification of the management system. In addition, artificial intelligence should be used to analyze web traffic to detect malicious actions. This prevents malicious code from entering the information system, detects and blocks identified malicious requests (Noja, 2019; Esposito & Dicorato, 2020). AI helps to create strong passwords and encryption keys, as well as to record suspicious activity of management process participants.

The involvement of artificial intelligence capabilities in the management process allows for optimal control and administration of user access to the information and resource database. It also guarantees selective access to confidential data. An additional positive bonus includes optimization of security control levels and effective identification of potential challenges in this area. This enables cloud providers to quickly identify and eliminate possible threats, thereby minimizing the risks of data leakage.

Today, there is a need to develop a perfect digitalization product that can guarantee a more convenient and secure format of communication in various areas of public administration. This issue is extremely urgent and requires special attention. A wide range of communications, as well as the process of implementing effective financial and administrative models in the socio-economic processes of society, depend on digital transformation. The implementation of the principles of modern effective public administration will help ensure the sustainable development of both individual local territories, communities, and the global community in the context of globalization. Based on the aforesaid, we can predict an increase in the role of public administration towards the implementation of the principles of sustainable development. This will allow to intensify its productivity in the direction of economic efficiency and minimization of environmental impact, in particular, through the introduction of innovative technological solutions and digital optimization capabilities.

Ukraine is currently implementing various reforms aimed at transitioning from the concept of state administration to the concept of public administration. At the same time, it is noteworthy that the democratization of management processes is based on the formation of a wide range of public self-governance. The most optimal approach involves the synergy of management processes with the possibilities of self-regulation of society, which are provided by modern tools of innovative

technologies. At present, the search for the most effective model of digitalization of public administration processes in the context of sustainable development is seen as a priority. It will create opportunities to improve the efficiency of management processes, intensify the effectiveness of economic processes, and strengthen the role of local development during the global transformation.

5 Discussion

The vast majority of modern scholars see innovative technological optimization of public administration of socio-economic processes as the basis for effective transformation towards sustainable development. In particular, some scholars (Strelcow et al., 2020) believe that the active influence of a public resource on the management decision-making process is a prerequisite for the successful implementation of public administration policy. In their opinion, the effectiveness of the management paradigm depends on the level of compliance with the needs of society in terms of technological innovation.

For some scientists (Lewallen, 2021; Guarini et al., 2021), the main positive effects of implementing AI-enabled management solutions are high speed of response to threats, minimization of information security management costs, reduction of the risk of data loss or unauthorized use and saving time for regular monitoring and security audits. A few scholars (Zuiderwijk et al., 2021) believe that the newest direction of artificial intelligence applications in the public administration system is to increase the level of cybersecurity of cloud providers by automated identification of potential threats.

Modern researchers (Tichenor et al., 2022; Yunita et al., 2022) argue that the improvement of the management process as part of its adaptation to the global digitalization process cannot be implemented in Ukraine following the European model. This is caused by the ambiguity of the internal environment's readiness for such a transformation. The authors have identified some factors that indicate both the readiness for digital transformation of the public administration system and those that impede its development. The introduction of remote work practices and the widespread use of information and communication technologies determine the urgency for encrypting sensitive data and the latest protection strategies.

A number of scientists (Marques et al., 2021; Krafft et al., 2022) have studied the identification of digitalization as a direction of

innovative development of public administration processes. They argue that crisis phenomena within society intensify the lack of state participation in the digitalization process. Representatives of current research directions (Benzaken et al., 2022) argue that the active use of digitalization tools is one of the most effective means to optimize the functioning of the public administration system. According to scholars, the main goal of the digital transformation process is to synergize data sets for optimal use. This goal can be achieved with the help of various effective algorithms. The authors emphasize that the process of digital optimization is influenced by multiple factors, including time constraints, financial capabilities, and the level of intellectual resources.

Modern researchers (Shandryk et al., 2023; Bouilloud et al., 2020) also consider digitalization to be the most promising direction for the development of the public administration system in the context of sustainable development. They emphasize that today, only a few areas of socio-economic processes can be considered consumers of innovative technological and managerial solutions. In this regard, it can be argued that insufficient access to modern technologies and unwillingness to implement them are the most significant factors limiting the potential of digital transformation within the public administration system.

Some scholars (Kankanhalli et al., 2019; Van Wynsberghe, 2021; Meier, 2023) believe that modern public administration based on digital methods is mainly an activity of a practical and advisory nature. It helps the service consumer to achieve goals and tasks by finding solutions to problems of various kinds, identifying new opportunities, implementing changes, and coaching. At the same time, scholars (Hutsaliuk et al., 2020; Trondal, 2021) identify specific prerequisites for the formation of an effective public administration system in the context of sustainable development. They include the availability of an appropriate resource base and the readiness of society for dynamic change. The scientists substantiate that such conditions are an essential component of the algorithm for implementing public administration in various spheres of socio-economic life, and it is difficult to disagree with them.

The scientific research of modern scholars (Magliacani, 2023; König et al., 2023) forms the belief that public administration within the context of sustainable development requires, first of all, digital support based on the principles of rational resource use. It will also need an increase in the efficiency of interaction between authorities at different levels of government, society, and business based on the principles of democratic balanced growth. Such an approach will help to accelerate the qualitative positive dynamics of society's transformation towards a sustainable approach to all spheres of life, ensure ecological reproduction of the resource potential, and make it possible to achieve financial stability of socio-economic processes.

The forecast of the trend of increasing importance of sustainable development principles indicates that in the future, the market demands of the industry will increasingly depend on the system of management decisions, where the principle of publicity should be a top priority. Based on the aforementioned conclusions, as well as the results of the current study, it can be argued that public administration in the context of sustainable development has significantly expanded the scope of its functioning today. It has become an essential element of the system to ensure the implementation of optimal balanced development. It should be noted that the effectiveness of implementing the principles of balanced development based on optimal public administration involves the gradual and effective achievement of goals through innovative opportunities and digitalization technologies.

6 Conclusion

This study proved that effective public administration is one of the crucial elements in the system of practical implementation of the sustainable development concept of modern society. It has

been found that innovative technologies, effective digitalization, and proper control by the state and society allow for the full and timely implementation of an effective public administration system in the context of sustainable development.

The research analyzed the potential of innovative capabilities of public administration, the main problems of applying innovative technologies in management processes, and variations of ways to solve them. The authors investigated the potential optimization capabilities of the public administration transformation process through innovative tools. Moreover, the article analyzed the experience of developed countries in public administration of the processes of society's life, as well as its public administration, legal, and organizational aspects. The authors investigated the feasibility and prospects of using innovative electronic systems and the capabilities of modern tools and technologies to optimize the public administration system.

A practical approach to public administration in the context of global digitalization and the rapid development of innovative technologies will ensure the successful adaptation of society to the necessary socio-economic transformations. It should be based on implementing a development strategy shaped by the principle of unimpeded access to information in a convenient format. Currently, the search for the most effective model for the practical implementation of the public administration strategy in the context of sustainable development involving the wide capabilities of digital tools is considered a top priority. Such a model will maximize the efficiency and accessibility of information resources and strengthen the priority status of transformations based on sustainable development in all spheres of socio-economic life.

Further research on this topic should be aimed at a detailed identification of the conditions for systemic integration of digitalization tools, taking into account the current capabilities of the existing electronic and communication base of administrative systems.

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